

AICEI PROCEEDINGS

The Workplace as Motivator: A Comparative Study of Employees in Business and Public Administration in Macedonia and Neighboring Countries

Marjan Bojadziev, Nikica Mojsoska Blazevski, Desislava Boshnakova, Miodraga Stefanovska, Venera Krliu, Jasminka Janakievaska and Valon Saracini

Abstract

Job satisfaction is important because of its effects on employees' performance and behavior (Oshagbemi, 1999). Prior studies have shown a close connection between job satisfaction and organizational outcomes (Meyer et al., 1989; Bitner, 1990; Tett et al., 1993; Locke&Latham, 1990) and personal outcomes such as workplace turnover and life satisfaction (Judge et al. 2001; Dickter et al., 1996; Morrison, 1997). Recent papers suggest that while a good deal of empirical research has been conducted on job satisfaction in various business settings (Nikolescu et al., 2009), very little empirical research has investigated cross-country differences in levels of job satisfaction and motivation. This paper identifies and examines the factors which contribute to job satisfaction and motivation amongst white collar employees at the workplace in four countries at different stages of EU membership: the Republic of Macedonia, Kosovo (UNMIK), Bulgaria and Turkey.

The results of this study are expected to contribute to the identification of organizational issues related to job satisfaction and employee motivation in both the for-profit and not-for-profit sectors. The availability of these results will facilitate future efforts by behavioral scientists to understand disparities in the effectiveness of job enrichment methods between countries at different stages of EU integration and economic development. In addition, results from previous studies (Hackman and Oldham, 1974; Kamdron, 2005) will be used as control group.

Keywords: job description, Macedonia, Kosovo, Bulgaria, Turkey, employees

The Problem and the Main Targets of the Research

Job satisfaction greatly influences work performance (Robbins, Judge 2009). Job design strongly influences job satisfaction. The purpose of this paper is to examine the influences of workplaces as a driving force that leads to job satisfaction and motivation. "The old way of managing and looking at work isn't going to work anymore" (Conlin, 2006). But, what is the new way? It can be described as the design of workplaces that create job satisfaction and motivation. The aim of this research, which should serve as a pilot study (due to its scope) is to identify key differences between 3 countries at different stages of the EU accession process: Bulgaria, a recent EU member; Macedonia, an EU candidate; and Kosovo, which is not yet an EU candidate. In addition, we provide comparative analysis with an older EU member country, Estonia, which comes from the same group of southeastern and central European countries (SEE). We believe that our pilot study will initiate further research that would explore the impact of the Lisbon Treaty on diminishing cultural differences among SEE nations.

Hypotheses

What has been the impact of the Lisbon Treaty? What has been the impact of the EU accession process? The working hypotheses adopted for this pilot study can be defined as follows: EU integration diminishes cultural differences between European nations, making the economies of the EU countries more competitive and public administration more efficient. The Lisbon Treaty is one of the milestones on that journey.

In particular, this pilot study provides a basis for comparing the effects of EU integration on one of the aspects of cultural diversity, the Job Characteristics Model (JCM) of job satisfaction and Motivational Potential Score. Comparison is made across countries that are at different stages of EU accession/membership. Therefore, the specific hypothesis of the study can be formulated as follows: The EU integration (process) influences the motivation and satisfaction of employees; hence there are differences in motivational factors between countries which shared similar pre-accession cultures and economic-political systems but which are now at different stages of EU accession/membership.

Recent studies on “comparable countries” (former socialist countries that have applied for EU membership) state that hygienic factors have a predominant influence on job motivation (Kamdron, 2005). The higher the educational level of employees, the more the factors connected with the content of the job are evaluated. Similar results have also been identified for the Republic of Macedonia (Bojadziev and Krlju, 2006).

Methods

Our analysis is methodologically based on the original Job Diagnostic Survey (JDS) of Hackman and Oldham (1974). The JDS is a widely accepted tool and method used to conduct comparative assessments in each of the relevant sectors that are foreseen in this study. The results of the original work of Hackman and Oldham are used together with the results from Kamdron’s survey as control groups for the purposes of this paper. Of the three approaches proposed by Kamdron, we have focused on the need – strength.

We have conducted a cross-country and cross-section analysis with the JDS. The former dimension is captured by investigating job satisfaction in three countries, Bulgaria, Kosovo and Macedonia; the latter dimension is captured by including business sector, public administration and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). We believe that there are differences in both dimensions of the study, i.e. by countries and by sectors. For the analysis, we use convenience sampling as a nonprobability sampling technique. A relatively small convenient sample is used in the study by using elements that are not pre-specified or without any known possibility of being selected. Although there is an ongoing discussion on the possibility of evaluating the “goodness” of the sample in terms of its representativeness of the population and the quality of results, still many researchers argue that convenience sampling can be treated as though it were a probability sample (Anderson *et al.*, 2009). Since this is one of the first studies to have explored the issue of job satisfaction and motivation in Bulgaria, Macedonia and Kosovo, we do not seek to make inferences for the whole population but only to provide an initial insight into the situation.

The JDS can be used to measure the level of job satisfaction and motivation among employees in almost all sectors. The results of the JDS can be used to determine whether the level of enrichment of a job is sufficient to

ensure a desired level of satisfaction and motivation on the part of the employee.

The study of Bulgaria was carried out only among business sector employees. The rationale for this decision was that Bulgaria is the only EU member state of the countries which participated in this study. The assumption of this paper was that the design, organization and 'evolutionary stage' of public administration in an EU member state as compared to a candidate member country such as Macedonia and a newly founded aspiring member state such as Kosovo would produce divergent results in favor of Bulgaria (since the comparison is among three diverging PA structures). This is supported by studies that have been undertaken in the last 20 years in the field of public administration. Each of them examines countries with similar structures and objectives of public administration. For example, the quantitative Common Assessment Framework (CAF) was designed for benchmarking administrative performance in the context of the EU and in relation to the Lisbon Competitiveness Agenda (Staes and Thijis, 2006).

The analysis of NGOs was motivated by their role in developing countries as a form of global response to 'negative social scenarios' (Glatzer, 2002). This sector emerges as a response to short term or long term social deviations and acts to bring society back to a state of general well-being. The situation that characterized Macedonia and—even more so—Kosovo determined the structure and specialty of the NGOs that were established in these two countries. Thus they were mainly focused on promoting sustainable peace, stimulating inter-cultural dialogue, improving health education, etc. Therefore the comparison of the NGO sector in this research is made only between Kosovo and Macedonia in order to generate comparable results.

Descriptive Analysis

The total sample size included in this study is 54. The sample distribution among the three countries in which the study was conducted is as follows: Bulgaria (14.84%), Kosovo (48.15%) and Macedonia (37.01%). As Table 1 shows, among the participants in the study, females were dominant in Macedonia (65.38%) and Bulgaria (100%). In contrast, the participants in Kosovo were predominantly male (65%). The total sample contained more participants belonging to the age group 30–39 and less in the age-group from 50–59. Macedonian participants were the 'youngest': over 90 per cent of the

participants in the study were aged 20–39 years, while Kosovo had the highest number of participants aged 40–49.

Procedures

Questionnaires were distributed and collected upon completion. No coaching on the questionnaire and how it should be completed was provided.

The study was carried out among randomly chosen employees in three main sectors: public administration, business, and the non-governmental sector. In Bulgaria the study was carried out only among business sector employees. The business sector was dominant in Macedonia (69.23%) and Kosovo (50%). In terms of education, the majority of participants possessed university education (Bulgaria 25%; Macedonia 61.54% and Kosovo 35%), a master's degree or higher qualification (Bulgaria 37.5%, Macedonia 61.54% and Kosovo 10%).

Table 1

Demographic characteristics of the sample ($N_{TOTAL} = 54$)	Bulgaria ($N_B=8$)		Macedonia ($N_M=26$)		Kosovo ($N_K=20$)	
		%		%		%
Male			9	34.62	13	65.00
Female	8	100	17	65.38	7	35.00
AGE						
<20						
20–29	2	25	11	42.31	5	25.00
30–39	5	62.5	13	50.00	6	30.00
40–49	1	12.5	1	3.85	8	40.00
50–59			1	3.85	1	5.00
60<						
EDUCATION						
grade school						
some high school						
high school diploma			3	11.54	11	55.00
some business college or technical school	1	12.5	1	3.85		

experience						
some college experience (other than business or technical school)	1	12.5				
business college to technical school degree						
college degree	1	12.5				
some graduate work	2	25	7	26.92	7	35.00
Master's or higher postgraduate qualification	3	37.5	15	61.54	2	10.00
SECTOR						
Business	8	100	18	69.23	10	50.00
Public Administration			4	15.38	5	25.00
NGO			4	15.38	5	25.00

Results of the Job Diagnostic Survey

The results from the study (per sector and per country) are presented in Table 1 below and provide an initial picture of the differences in job motivation and job satisfaction in all three countries in which the study was implemented.

Table 1. Results from the JDS survey among employees from the business sector, NGOs and public administration in Kosovo, Macedonia and Bulgaria

Job qualities	Kosovo BS	Kosovo PA	Kosovo NGO	Bulgaria	Mac BS	Mac PA	Mac NGO
Skill variety	4.37 (1.10)	4.33 (1.11)	4.33 (0.72)	5.58 (1.48)	5.75 (0.99)	5.67 (1.78)	5.33 (1.29)
Task identity	4.6 (1.16)	4.13 (1.06)	3.27 (0.96)	5.08 (1.64)	4.92 (1.57)	5.83 (1.34)	4.67 (1.61)
Task significance	4.17 (1.13)	4.6 (1.03)	3.4 (1.03)	5.31 (1.53)	4.06 (0.83)	4.58 (2.23)	4.08 (1.17)
Autonomy	4.2 (1.71)	3.4 (1.40)	3.33 (1.11)	5.28 (1.36)	5.55 (0.92)	5.42 (1.24)	4.33 (1.63)
Feedback from the job itself	5.2 (1.24)	5.6 (0.74)	5.27 (0.46)	5.33 (1.50)	5.23 (1.41)	4.42 (2.27)	5.53 (1.21)
Feedback from agents	5.1 (0.96)	4.87 (0.64)	4.67 (0.98)	5.83 (1.02)	4.63 (1.65)	5.83 (1.64)	5.39 (1.03)

Dealing with others	4.9 (1.95)	5.07 (0.79)	4.53 (1.8)	5.81 (1.28)	6.19 (1.14)	5.58 (1.62)	5.25 (1.36)
Experienced meaningfulness	6.03 (0.70)	5.75 (0.85)	5.55 (0.89)	5.78 (1.24)	5.71 (1.22)	4.88 (2.31)	6.13 (0.83)
Experienced responsibility	5.5 (1.09)	4.83 (1.59)	4.97 (1.10)	5.31 (1.54)	5.29 (1.91)	5.54 (1.97)	5.68 (1.77)
Knowledge of results	4.25 (1.81)	5.15 (1.53)	4.85 (1.39)	5.5 (1.45)	5.63 (1.22)	4.81 (1.76)	5.13 (1.88)
General satisfaction	4.76 (1.13)	5.4 (0.50)	4.84 (0.90)	5.5 (1.43)	4.66 (1.35)	4.55 (2.09)	5.7 (1.67)
Internal work motivation	5.1 (0.68)	5.67 (1.12)	4.97 (1.03)	5.35 (1.95)	5.47 (1.30)	4.92 (1.98)	5.65 (1.15)
“Pay” satisfaction	5.6 (0.50)	5.5 (0.53)	5.5 (0.53)	4.42 (1.50)	4.74 (1.70)	2.75 (0.89)	5.13 (1.46)
“Security” satisfaction	5.3 (0.66)	5 (1.05)	5.1 (0.99)	5.21 (1.12)	5.08 (1.28)	4.5 (1.77)	5 (1.20)
“Social” satisfaction	6.47 (0.76)	5.6 (0.51)	5.13 (0.83)	5.81 (1.14)	5.6 (1.35)	5.5 (1.57)	6.08 (0.79)
“Supervisory” satisfaction	5.33 (0.48)	5 (0.00)	5.27 (0.59)	5.44 (1.42)	4.86 (1.62)	3.17 (1.19)	4.58 (1.68)
“Growth” satisfaction	5.6 (0.92)	4.75 (0.44)	4.65 (0.81)	5.33 (1.27)	5.41 (1.43)	4.63 (2.09)	5.63 (1.02)
Desirable aspect at work	5.73 (0.52)	5.5 (0.63)	5.7 (0.60)	5.63 (1.51)	5.85 (1.36)	6.42 (0.65)	6.21 (0.93)
Job choice	3.6 (1.39)	3.13 (1.35)	3.64 (1.34)	4.71 (1.67)	4.09 (1.44)	4.46 (1.43)	3.33 (1.52)
MPS	95.6	82.9	64.35	149.8	142.5	128.4	112.4

NB: Standard deviations for each variable are shown in brackets

JDS Results for the Business and Public Administration Sector in Kosovo, Bulgaria and Macedonia

Discussion of the results of the JDS among business sector and public administration employees in Kosovo, Macedonia and Bulgaria (Table 1) is organized in five main sections related to the main divisions provided by Hackman and Oldham (1987). The presentation of the results in such a format enables a more straightforward comparison and examination of the

characteristics of jobs and employee reactions to business sector and public administration jobs in Macedonia, Kosovo and Bulgaria.

I. Job Diagnostic

1. The Skill Variety dimension measured (1) the degree to which a variety of different activities are required to perform a certain job; and (2) whether the job involves the use of the employee's different skills and talents. The results from the survey indicate that jobs in the business sector in Macedonia are characterized with the highest score on 'skill variety', followed by business sector employees in Bulgaria and Kosovo (Graph 1). However, a closer look at the results shows that the scores on this job dimension are similar among employees in the business sectors in Macedonia and Bulgaria, in comparison to the employees in Kosovo. Interestingly, public administration employees in Kosovo and Macedonia report the same level of skill variety in jobs as employees in the business sector in the respective countries.

(Graph 2)

2. The second of the seven job dimensions is that of task identity. This dimension measures the degree to which the job requires completion of a 'whole' and identifiable piece of work. The findings from the business sector suggest that Bulgarian employees experience the highest degree of task identity (5.08), followed by Macedonia (4.92) and Kosovo (4.6). The results suggest that there are smaller differences between business sector employees in Macedonia and Kosovo in regards to this job dimension. By contrast, the difference is higher among public administration employees. The JDS results show that the employees in public administration in Macedonia have the highest scores compared to employees across the two relevant

sectors in characterizing their job as a “from the beginning to the end” process that results in a tangible outcome.

Graph 3 - Task identity in business sector jobs

Graph 4 - Task identity in public administration jobs

3. Interestingly, employees in Kosovo and Macedonia from both from the public administration and business sectors have a very similar rating regarding the task significance of their jobs. This dimension indicates the degree to which a job has a substantial impact on the lives or work of other people, whether in the immediate organization or in the external environment. In the business sector, Bulgarian employees rate their jobs with a higher level of task significance compared to those in Kosovo and Macedonia. In general, Macedonian employees show a slightly higher rate of task significance of their jobs compared to employees from Kosovo. In terms of cross-sector comparison, public administration employees in both Kosovo and Macedonia show a higher level rating regarding the task significance of their jobs compared to employees from the business sector in each of these countries.

Graph 5 - Task significance in business sector jobs

Graph 6 - Task significance in public administration jobs

4. Public administration employee experience the lowest degree of autonomy

on the job in general. This is especially evident amongst employees in public administration in Kosovo, whose score of 3.4 suggests that they tend towards a negative rating regarding substantial freedom, independence, discretion in scheduling work and in determining procedures for the realization of tasks. In contrast, public and business sector employees in Macedonia have the 'highest level of autonomy' in their jobs, slightly higher than business sector employees in Bulgaria.

Graph 7 - Job autonomy in business sector jobs

Graph 8 - Job autonomy in public administration jobs

5. Employees in Macedonia, Kosovo and Bulgaria report similar ratings for the feedback they get from their job. This means that employees in these three countries receive clear and direct information about the effectiveness of their individual performance. However, when comparing sectors across countries, it can be noted that public administration employees in Macedonia receive the lowest levels of feedback from their job.

Graph 9 - Feedback from the job itself in business sector jobs

Graph 10 - Feedback from the job itself in public administration jobs

Another way in which employees assess their performance on the job is through the feedback they get from their supervisors and co-workers. The results of the survey show that the highest degree of feedback is reported by

employees in the public administration in Macedonia (5.83) and employees from the business sector in Bulgaria (5.83). Contrary to expectations, Macedonian business sector employees report receiving a lower level of feedback from their supervisors and co-workers compared to employees in public administration in Macedonia, which is probably due to the performance-related pay system implemented among civil servants in Macedonia. However, results from Kosovo show the opposite: business sector employees have higher feedback levels than those employed in public administration.

Jobs in the business sector in Macedonia are also characterized by a high degree of interaction with other people, both internal and external to the organization. On the other hand, the same sector jobs in Kosovo are characterized by the lowest degree of requirements for employees to work closely with other people in fulfilling their expected tasks. Employees in the Bulgarian business sector have a similar degree of cooperation with co-workers and clients, though slightly lower compared to Macedonian employees.

II. Critical Psychological States

The following discussion of the results intends to provide an insight into each of the three psychological states that mediate between the core job dimension and the outcomes of the work. These comprise the (1) Experienced meaningfulness of the work; (2) Experienced responsibility for work; and (3) Knowledge of results. The results will be discussed in this order.

Graph 11 - Experienced meaningfulness of the work in business sector jobs

Graph 12 - Experienced meaningfulness of the work in public administration jobs

As can be seen on Graph 11, business sector employees in Kosovo have the most positive experience of their jobs as meaningful, valuable and

worthwhile, though the difference with the other two countries is quite small. A cross-country comparison of employees in public administration suggests that Macedonian employees have a significantly lower degree of experiencing meaningfulness in their work (4.88), compared to Kosovo (5.75). As the results presented in Graph 12 suggest, although the degree of meaningfulness of work is low among public administration employees in Macedonia, the degree to which these employees feel personally accountable and responsible for the work they do is much higher compared to public administration employees in Kosovo. This suggests that the experience of responsibility among public administration employees in both countries does not depend on the personal experience of the meaningfulness of the job. However, the case is the opposite in the business sector where we can see a clear link between the degrees of experienced responsibility and experienced meaningfulness among employees.

Graph 13 - Experienced responsibility in business sector jobs

Graph 14 - Experienced responsibility in public administration jobs

Business sector employees in Macedonia have the highest degree of knowledge and understanding on a continuous basis regarding the effectiveness of their job. Cross-country and cross-sector comparison suggests the business sector employees from Kosovo do not have clear and continuous information about the results of the jobs they are performing. It seems important to note here that these are the same employees that reported the highest degree of meaningfulness and responsibility in their work. While having the highest degree of experiencing job responsibility, employees from public administration in Macedonia report one of the lowest degrees of continuous and understandable knowledge of results about their job effectiveness. This may be one of the reasons why these employees may not experience their jobs as being as meaningful and valuable as employees in other sectors. This is also supported by results from public administration

employees in Kosovo: a high degree of experiencing job meaningfulness is positively associated with the degree of knowledge of results, and both are negatively associated with the experience of responsibility for work. The results may suggest an interesting insight into public administration employees in these two countries: the level of characterizing their work as meaningful, valuable and worthwhile depends on frequency and clarity of information about their effectiveness and performance on the job.

Graph 15 - Knowledge of results in business sector jobs

Graph 14 - Knowledge of results in public administration jobs

III. Affective Reactions to the Job

This section discusses affective reactions to jobs—also referred to in the literature as ‘personal outcomes’ obtained from performing a job. These are measures of personal, affective reactions—the feelings that a person obtains from doing a job.

The results from this study suggest that in the business sector Bulgarian employees have the highest score in terms of general satisfaction. This means that Bulgarian business sector employees are on average happier and more satisfied with their jobs than employees in the same sector in Macedonia and Kosovo, who show similar level of general job satisfaction. Public sector employees in Kosovo show a higher level of satisfaction with their jobs in comparison with Macedonian public administration employees. It is very interesting to note that the cross-sector and cross-country analysis of data suggests that public administration employees in Kosovo have a very similar high score of general job satisfaction as employees in the business sector in Kosovo. Furthermore, contrary to general expectations, public and business sector employees in Macedonia have similar levels of general job satisfaction (although this is slightly higher for the business sector).

Internal work motivation relates to the degree to which an employee is self-motivated to perform effectively on the job. Graph 15 shows that Macedonian employees in the business sector have the highest level of internal work motivation, followed by Bulgaria and Kosovo. In other words, Macedonian employees have the highest possibility of feeling good upon the completion of their work.

In accordance with the results from the cross-sector and cross-country analysis, the data suggests that public administration employees in Kosovo have the highest degree of self-motivation to perform effectively on the job.

The specific satisfaction indicators provide separate measures of job satisfaction on the following scales: pay satisfaction, security satisfaction, social satisfaction, supervisory satisfaction and growth satisfaction. The results in this category show:

- satisfaction with pay and other compensation is the highest among civil servants in Kosovo (5.50) and lowest among the same category of employees in Macedonia (2.75);
- business sector employees in Kosovo are very satisfied with the social attributes of their jobs, i.e. peers and co-workers (6.47). Cross-sector and cross-country analysis shows that both public administration and business sector employees have a high degree of social satisfaction;
- Macedonian public administration (4.86) and business sector employees (3.17) show the lowest levels of 'supervisory' satisfaction compared to the other countries in the study. Business sector employees are not satisfied with the supervision over their jobs;
- Business sector employees across the three countries have higher opportunities for personal growth and development on the job ('growth' satisfaction) compared to public administration employees. In other words, these employees are more willing to improve and translate acquired knowledge into practice compared to those working in public administration;
- All employees expressed similar levels of job security (all above 5), with the exception of lower levels of job security experienced by Macedonian employees in public administration (4.50).

Chart 15-Comparison of affective reactions to the job among business sector employees

Chart 16 - Comparison of affective reactions to the job among public administration employees

IV. Individual Growth, Needs, Strength

Data from the 'individual growth, need, strength' section also shows that people prefer enriched work (desired aspects of work is higher compared to job choice). Most preferable is work where one can find more room for innovation, more communication, more training possibilities, more independence and free time. The job choice results indicate that business

sector employees in all three countries have a higher degree of internal work motivation and growth satisfaction compared to employees in public administration.

V. Motivating Potential Score (MPS)

The motivating potential score (MPS) among business sector employees is highest in Bulgaria (150), followed by Macedonia (142) and Kosovo (96). However, the MPS among public administration employees is generally lower compared to those in the business sector. In Macedonia it is 128, while Kosovo has a very low MPS among its public administration (82.9).

VI. JDS Results: the NGO Sector in Kosovo and Macedonia

The results from the JDS among employees in the NGO sector are presented in Table 1. The findings from the research in this sector suggest that employees in the NGO sector in Macedonia experience their jobs in a more positive way compared to their counterparts in Kosovo. The MPS for Macedonia is almost twice as high as that for Kosovo.

I. Job Dimensions

The results show that Macedonian NGO sector jobs are characterized by a higher degree of different activities and the involvement of a variety of skills and talents needed in order to complete the job. NGO sector employees from Kosovo do not experience their jobs as a “beginning to an end” process with a clear outcome. It is interesting to note that respondents from Kosovo identify their jobs as not having an impact on the lives and work of other people. This is contrary to common expectations since the core motivation and objective of the NGO sector is to make a positive difference in the immediate and extended surrounding. However, NGO activists from both countries were able to visualize and understand the results of the jobs they were doing. In accordance with expectations, NGO employees from Kosovo and Macedonia indicated that their jobs required them to work closely with other people (this score is higher for Macedonia). It is important to declare an assumption at this stage: the high scores for Macedonian NGO employees can be attributed to the mission of their NGOs. The NGOs which participated in the survey work

closely on a day-to-day basis with vulnerable groups and NGOs have been functioning in Macedonia for more than five years. This may explain the reported dynamics, variety and increased contacts of the NGO sector in Macedonia.

II. Critical Psychological States

This part of the JDS is especially important in providing an insight into the NGO sector since it measures the psychological impact that the job has on the employee. As the results show, NGO employees from both countries have higher scores in this section, which is to be expected from employees in this sector. The highest score is observed in terms of the degree to which the employee feels that his/her job is generally meaningful, valuable and worthwhile. Although the scores are higher for Macedonia, NGO activists in both countries feel accountable and responsible for the work they do, as well as reporting that they continuously know and understand how effectively they are performing.

III. Affective Reactions

One particularly interesting area of the JDS in which Kosovo demonstrates higher results concerns the private, affective reactions that the employee gets from working on the job. The results of the study suggest that Macedonian employees in the NGO sector have the highest score in *general satisfaction*. In other words, this means that Macedonian employees in the NGO sector are on average happier and more satisfied with their job compared to employees in the NGO sector in Kosovo. *Internal work motivation* measures the degree to which an employee is self-motivated to perform effectively on the job. Macedonian employees in the NGO sector have a higher level of internal work motivation. In other words, these employees have the highest possibility of feeling good after the completion of their work. Employees in the Kosovo NGO sector shows higher results in terms of satisfaction with supervision and security, while employees in the Macedonian NGO sector are more satisfied with their pay and with the social and growth aspects of their work.

IV. Individual Growth Need Strength Model

Analysis of results in this section indicates that NGO employees in both countries prefer enriched work (based on a comparison of the score of desired aspects of work with job choice). Employees prefer work where they can find more training possibilities, more innovation, more communication within and outside the organization, and greater independence and free time.

III. Comparison with Results from Previous JDS Surveys

The results of the JDS (means) for Macedonia, Bulgaria, Kosovo, the USA, Finland and Estonia are presented in Table 1. The Estonian and Finnish median indicators are drawn from Kamdrón (2005). The US JDS means are derived from the Hackmans and Oldhams JDS survey. It is interesting to note that a cross-country comparison of results shows similar results as in Kamdrón (2005), i.e., the average indicators of the JDS among Estonian higher officials exceed the corresponding averages obtained from all other countries presented in Table 2.

Job qualities	Kosovo	Bulgaria	Macedonia	Estonia HO	USA	Finland	Estonia
Skill variety	4.34	5.58	5.58	5.95	4.49	4.1	5
Task identity	4.00	5.08	5.14	4.47	4.87	4.51	4.4
Task significance	4.06	5.31	4.24	5.62	5.49	4.58	5
Autonomy	3.64	5.28	5.10	5.38	4.8	4.71	5
Feedback from the job itself	5.36	5.33	5.06	5.05	4.98	4.55	5
Feedback from agents	4.88	5.83	5.28	3.96	3.98	3.2	3.5
Dealing with others	4.83	5.81	5.67	6.34	5.29	4.78	5.6
Experienced meaningfulness	5.78	5.78	5.57	5.65	5.12	4.76	2.9
Experienced responsibility for work	5.10	5.31	5.50	6.04	5.48	5.28	5.5
Knowledge of results	4.75	5.5	5.19	5.07	5.18	4.91	3.8

General satisfaction	5.00	5.5	4.97	4.94	4.62	4.42	3.8
Internal work motivation	5.25	5.35	5.35	6.18	5.39	4.96	5.5
“Pay” satisfaction	5.53	4.42	4.21	4.19		3.14	3.9
“Security” satisfaction	5.13	5.21	4.86	4.05		5.12	4.4
“Social” satisfaction	5.73	5.81	5.73	5.98	5.42	5.07	5.4
“Supervisory” satisfaction	5.20	5.44	4.20	5.08	5.28	4.17	4.4
“Growth” satisfaction	5.00	5.33	5.22	5.66	4.82	4.4	4.7
Desirable aspect at work	5.64	5.63	6.16	5.72	5.62	4.83	
Job choice	3.46	4.71	3.96	3.59		3.03	
MPS	80.95	149.81	127.77	159.05	128	104	120

Although lower, Bulgaria shows high scores similar to the Estonian higher officials. The MPS is measured on a scale with a maximum value of 300. In the case of Estonian higher officials it is 159, followed by Bulgaria with an approximate score of 149.

The highest assessment in terms of job enrichment, which is common to all countries presented in Table 2, is given to the rate of dealing with others, skill variety and dealing with the job itself. In this context, Macedonia ranks among the highest scores in skill variety and degree of feedback from agents.

Analysis of the results shows that employees from Macedonia, Bulgaria or Kosovo feel happier and more satisfied with their work than employees in other countries presented in Table 2. In addition, employees from these three countries demonstrate that they have a similar level of self-motivation to perform effectively on the job as Estonian, US and Finnish employees. It is also interesting to note that, in terms of specific satisfactions with the job, employees in Kosovo have the highest satisfaction in terms of their salary (5.53). Bulgaria leads in the degree of supervisory satisfaction (5.44) reported by employees, while Macedonia has one of the highest scores in growth and social satisfaction.

Data also indicates that people prefer enriched work (based on a comparison of scores of desired aspects of work with job choice). Employees prefer work where they can find more training possibilities, more innovation,

more communication within and outside the organization, and greater independence and free time for employees.

The jobs in all countries show a similar psychological impact on employees. This means that the majority of employees experience their jobs as meaningful, feel accountable for the work they do and have continuous information about how effective they are in their work.

Conclusion

I. Job dimensions The job dimension scores which measure the objective characteristics of the job itself from an employee's perspective were higher for Macedonian public administration employees than for employees in the same sector in Kosovo.

II. Critical Psychological States (as perceived) have shown similar results for the three countries and the two sectors. However, Macedonia performed lowest, especially in public administration, while Kosovo scored highest. This may be due to the "creation of new independent country and the sense of responsibility and meaningfulness."

III. Affective Reactions. The affective reactions of public administration employees in Kosovo were higher than those for Macedonian employees (pay satisfaction in Kosovo was 5.50 compared to 2.75 for Macedonia).

These findings are important in terms of the 'appropriateness' of the public administration model. Public administration capacity was one of the benchmarks for the evaluation of Macedonia's accession capacity, and most probably it will be one of the main issues in the process of negotiations.

In addition, public administration is linked to service delivery mechanisms. In the case of Macedonia, there is an especially in close connection with the Doing Business reforms. This means that in order to improve service delivery there is a need for motivated and performance driven administration and innovative tools in service delivery (Verheijen, 2007). Business sector employees from Bulgaria had the highest scores in general (even compared to previous research which was used for setting benchmarks). They were followed by Macedonian business sector employees, while Kosovo was characterized with the lowest scores. However the higher scores of the

business sector can be attributed to greater flexibility and faster job redesign in this sector.

IV. Individual growth needs strength also varies between countries, with Macedonia performing the highest. However, the differences cannot be considered significant.

V. MPS

The results from the JDS show a very low motivating potential score (MPS) for employees in public administration in Kosovo as compared to Macedonia. The MPS for Macedonian NGOs is almost twice as high as the one for Kosovo. The findings from research in this sector suggest that employees in the NGO sector in Macedonia experience their jobs in a more positive way than employees in Kosovo. A common finding from all sectors and countries considered in this study is that people prefer enriched work (based on a comparison of the scores of desired aspects of work with job choice). Employees prefer jobs with more training opportunities, jobs characterized by innovation, and jobs providing greater communication within and outside the organization, independence and free time for the employee.

The following general conclusion can be drawn: There are differences amongst the three countries which are expected to diminish as a result of European integration. In addition, EU integration is expected to improve the performance of these countries both in the business and the public sector.

The Lisbon Treaty is a milestone in the process of European integration. Further research is needed to monitor the development of the abovementioned processes.

Closing Remarks

This study is among the first undertaken to assess the level of job satisfaction and motivation among business sector, public administration and NGO employees in Macedonia, Kosovo and Bulgaria. Two main things should be taken into consideration when reading the paper:

This study was planned and implemented as a pilot study in order to gain an initial understanding of the level of job motivation and satisfaction amongst employees in the relevant sectors. Its results should be used as a guide in designing, planning and implementing future research in the area;

Although the sample is small in size, it should be taken into consideration that what the study assesses is the 'people' component of any job, sector or system. It uses the JDS as an accepted tool and method for obtaining this measurement. While such assessments can never be exact and can result in a divergence of interpretations, they still provide a clear indication of the how an employee experiences his/her job.

The review of the JDS results regarding employee job satisfaction and motivation provides a mixed picture of an evident need for reforms in the NGO sector and public administration and some promising developments in the business sector. The setbacks in public administration can be assumed to have larger implications since they affect key aspects of the public management system (civil service). According to Glatzer (2002), the absence of a well functioning HRM system and a motivating and fulfilling job environment has been one of most common obstacles faced in creating a state of the art public administration system.

In conclusion, this study is among the first steps taken to explore the issue of work motivation and satisfaction amongst employees in these countries and its results and findings should be taken as initial guides in the design of future research.

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